
The Application of ELSA Speak in English Learning to Improve Speaking Skills: Case in Hospitality Students Majoring in Tourism at Kupang State Polytechnic

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Article history:

Received: 12/ 03/ 2026 , Accepted: 16/04/2026 , Published: 30/ 05/ 2025

Keywords

AI
Elsa Speak
English
Students
Hospitality

Abstract

This study investigates the effectiveness of the ELSA Speak application in improving the English-speaking skills of hospitality students in the Tourism Department at Kupang State Polytechnic. Using ELSA Speak as a learning companion and assessment tool, the study evaluates its impact on students' speaking performance while identifying the benefits and challenges of its implementation. The findings indicate that ELSA Speak effectively enhances students' pronunciation, confidence, and overall speaking ability through objective feedback and regular practice. However, students continue to face difficulties in fluency and intonation. Limited vocabulary reduces speaking fluency, while regional language influence affects intonation, particularly in interrogative expressions and customer-service communication. The study also identifies external challenges, including unstable internet access, subscription costs, and limited functionality in the free version of the application. Overall, ELSA Speak is an effective technology-assisted learning tool for hospitality English instruction, although addressing linguistic and technical constraints is essential to maximize its effectiveness.

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1. Introduction

In the rapidly evolving digital era, artificial intelligence (AI) has become one of the most prominent and influential technological innovations. This technology has penetrated almost all aspects of our lives, including in the context of information systems (Wulantari, et al. (2023), Rusmiyanto, et al. (2023)). Artificial intelligence refers to the ability of computers to learn and adapt from data and make decisions automatically without human intervention. This capability has brought significant changes in how information systems are implemented, operated, and utilized. The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology opens up new opportunities for independent and interactive learning. In the digital era, artificial intelligence (AI) has become an integral part of various aspects of life, including education. The use of artificial intelligence in educational contexts can already be identified in several countries. For example, in Australia, an Intelligent Tutoring System has been developed to help address the imbalance between the number of educators and students (Luckin & Holmes, 2016). Furthermore, there is the Reciprocal Human-Machine Learning (RHML) theory, an interdisciplinary approach that emphasizes reciprocal learning between humans and AI systems (Scwartz, 2023). In this educational context, AI means that educators and students not only receive information from AI but also provide feedback that enables AI to learn and develop. This approach maintains the role of humans in learning while leveraging AI's capabilities to enhance the educational process. Furthermore, generative AI, such as the large language model (LML) GPT-4, has been integrated into intelligent learning systems to create more personalized and adaptive learning experiences. This AI is capable of dynamically generating content, providing real-time feedback, and adjusting learning paths according to individual student needs. However, challenges such as pedagogical accuracy, bias in AI models, and student engagement are major concerns in its implementation.

AI applications have spread across various fields of study. In addition to education, the world of tourism, particularly the hospitality industry, is also involved. AI has a significant impact on the tourism industry, particularly the hospitality industry. The use of AI in hospitality can improve operational efficiency, enhance the guest experience, and assist with data management and analysis. For example, AI can be used in automated reservation systems, chatbots for 24/7 customer service, personalized services based on guest preferences, room demand prediction, and guest feedback analysis to improve service quality (Wulantari et al. (2023)). Tourism industry players are expected to be more aware of every technological advancement, as this is closely related to their human resources and the quality of their service within the hospitality industry.

The hospitality industry is a service sector that demands high communication skills, particularly in English, an international language. English is a crucial skill in the hospitality industry, where interaction with guests from various countries is a primary requirement. In the increasingly global hospitality industry, English language proficiency has become a fundamental skill required for every employee, especially those on the front lines of hotel services such as receptionists, concierges, and customer service. English is not only used as a daily communication tool with foreign guests but also serves as an international standard for professional service. The use of English (English capacity) has become a primary model for the development of the tourism industry (Afifulloh, 2018:135), especially for the tourism industry targeting international tourists, for whom English is the primary language of communication. This fact is certainly closely related to the world of education, especially vocational education, which must address this issue more carefully. One area impacted is English language learning, particularly in vocational contexts such as hospitality study programs in vocational schools or universities. English is a key skill that students must master to face the demands of the global workplace, particularly in the hospitality industry, which demands cross-cultural and linguistic communication skills.

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A good command of English not only supports effective communication with international guests but also enhances graduates' competitiveness in the global job market. Hospitality students are required to master professional English, which encompasses speaking and listening skills, as well as vocabulary and expressions typical of the hospitality industry. However, the English language learning process in Indonesia often faces various obstacles, such as limited time for hands-on practice; classroom instruction sometimes provides insufficient or impersonal speaking practice tailored to each student's abilities; a lack of facilities to support interactive speaking practice; and many students still struggle to speak English fluently and confidently. They sometimes struggle with public speaking, particularly in areas such as pronunciation, fluency, and intonation. Environmental factors can also contribute to students' lack of access to accurate English learning. These obstacles can hinder their readiness to face the world of work, which demands high levels of communication skills.

Advances in artificial intelligence (AI) technology have indirectly opened up new opportunities in English learning, one of which is through the ELSA Speak (English Language Speech Assistant) application. ELSA Speak (English Language Speech Assistant) is an artificial intelligence (AI)-based English learning application designed to help users improve their speaking and pronunciation skills independently. This application uses speech recognition technology to detect pronunciation errors and provides real-time feedback, so users can correct and perfect their English pronunciation (Vu Van, 2015). According to research conducted by Dini et al. (2020), ELSA Speak is considered an innovation in improving English pronunciation skills in the Society era. This application has a positive influence on learning how to pronounce English, especially for students who are learning English as a foreign language. AI-based applications such as ELSA Speak offer a new approach in speech recognition technology and machine learning to provide real-time feedback on pronunciation, intonation, and fluency. This allows students to practice independently and receive direct, individualized correction.

However, the application of AI in the context of vocational English learning in Indonesia is still relatively limited and requires in-depth study regarding its effectiveness. This is the formulation of the problem that will be raised in this study, namely 1) how effective is the use of the ELSA Speak application in improving the English speaking skills (Pronunciation, fluency and intonation) of students majoring in Hospitality at the Kupang State Polytechnic, 2) what are the benefits obtained by students from the application of ELSA Speak technology in the process of learning English speaking?, and 3) what are the challenges and obstacles faced in the application of ELSA Speak for vocational English learning in the hospitality industry environment? Therefore, this study aims to explore and evaluate the effectiveness of the application of the ELSA Speak application in improving the speaking skills of students majoring in hospitality, as well as identifying the benefits and challenges faced in its implementation. Thus, it is hoped that this innovation can support a more interactive, adaptive, and relevant learning process to the needs of today's hospitality industry. The problem-solving approach in this study is carried out through several strategic stages. First, the needs and challenges faced by hospitality students in mastering English speaking skills were identified, such as shyness, lack of hands-on practice, and limited interactive facilities. Second, the development and implementation of AI technology, specifically the AI-based ELSA Speak, as an interactive and personalized speaking practice medium, allowing students to practice anytime and anywhere without social pressure. Third, the effectiveness of the AI use was evaluated by measuring the improvement in students' speaking skills and analyzing the benefits and challenges that emerged during implementation. This approach aims to create innovative solutions that can address the challenges of conventional learning and improve students' readiness to face the increasingly competitive world of work in the hospitality industry.

The state-of-the-art and novelty of this research includes the use of AI technology in education, specifically in improving students' speaking skills through AI-based applications such

as ELSA Speak. Furthermore, this research examines the relationship between English speaking skills and the needs of the hospitality industry. The use of AI for learning has been growing, with various intelligent systems and large language models (LLMs) capable of providing real-time feedback and tailoring learning paths to individual needs. However, the application of ELSA Speak in the context of vocational English learning in Indonesia remains limited and requires in-depth evaluation of its effectiveness.

The novelty of this research lies in its specific focus on Hospitality students and the use of the ELSA Speak application to improve speaking skills in an interactive and personalized manner. Furthermore, this research integrates an evaluative approach to the benefits and challenges of implementing AI-based ELSA Speak in the context of vocational learning, a practice that has been under-explored in Indonesia. Thus, this research offers innovation in the development of AI-based English learning solutions that are relevant to the needs of the hospitality industry and able to address the challenges of conventional learning at the vocational level. Several previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of ELSA Speak in educational contexts, but most of these studies have focused only on students in general or in regular teaching contexts, not specifically directed at professional communication needs, such as tourism students, who are required to have good oral communication skills in an international work environment. In addition, this study will also provide new insights regarding the implementation of technology in vocational education. Exploring how technology, especially AI-based applications such as ELSA Speak, can be integrated into English language learning in vocational institutions, particularly in the tourism sector related to the hospitality world. Thus, this study not only fills the gap in the existing literature but also provides a practical contribution to improving the quality of English language education in the Tourism Department.

Various previous studies have shown that the use of the English Language Speech Assistant (ELSA Speak) application positively contributes to improving English speaking skills, especially in pronunciation and fluency. Research conducted by Akhmad and Munawir (2022) at STKIP Kusuma Negara Jakarta found that the use of ELSA Speak significantly improved students' pronunciation skills and built their confidence in speaking. A similar finding was also found in research by Permatasari and Lubis (2024), which showed an increase in students' speaking skill scores after using ELSA Speak independently outside of class. Furthermore, Patmasari and Zaitun (2023) in a classroom action study at IAIN Pontianak noted an increase in students' fluency and accuracy after two cycles of application-based learning. Furthermore, a case study at Nha Trang University, Vietnam, reported that 91% of students experienced an improvement in speaking skills within three months of using ELSA Speak, with an average score increase of 17 points. Meanwhile, in the workplace, ELSA Speak has been used by several hospitality institutions, such as hotels and airlines, to train staff communication skills in serving international guests. However, while previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of ELSA Speak in general educational contexts, few studies have specifically examined its application to vocational education students, particularly in the tourism sector.

Yet, tourism students desperately need adequate English-speaking skills to communicate with foreign tourists and navigate the international workplace. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by exploring the effectiveness of ELSA Speak in improving the speaking skills of Tourism students at the Kupang State Polytechnic. Therefore, this research is expected to enrich the research literature in the field of English language learning technology and provide a practical contribution to improving the quality of vocational tourism graduates.

2. Materials and Methods

This study used an action research approach. This approach enabled the development and direct evaluation of the use of the ELSA Speak application in the learning process of hospitality students. Participants in this study were fifth-semester students of the Hospitality Study Program, Tourism Department, Kupang State Polytechnic. This study focused on improving the speaking skills of hospitality students. Furthermore, the main instrument used in this study was the ELSA Speak (English Language Speech Assistant) application. ELSA Speak is an artificial intelligence (AI)-based English learning application designed to help users improve their speaking and pronunciation skills independently. The application uses speech recognition technology to detect pronunciation errors and provide real-time feedback.

This research was conducted over a six-month period with the following strategic stages: a) Identification of Needs and Challenges: The initial stage involved identifying the needs and challenges faced by hospitality students in mastering English speaking skills, such as shyness, lack of direct practice, and limited interactive facilities. b) Development and Implementation of AI Technology: Developing and implementing AI technology, specifically the ELSA Speak application, as an interactive and personalized speaking practice medium. Students can practice anytime and anywhere without social pressure, c) Effectiveness Evaluation: Conducting an evaluation of the effectiveness of AI use through measuring the improvement of students' speaking skills, as well as analyzing the benefits and obstacles that arise during implementation.

This evaluation includes aspects of pronunciation, fluency, and intonation. Data collection is carried out through a) Observation: To assess the effectiveness of using the application in improving student competencies in a sustainable manner, b) Interviews: Conducted with students as informants to obtain their experiences and views regarding the use of the application, c) Reflection: The reflection process is used to evaluate the effectiveness of using the application, d) Real-time Feedback: The ELSA Speak application itself provides detailed real-time feedback on pronunciation errors at the word, syllable, and phoneme levels. The collected data was analyzed to: a) Assess the effectiveness of using ELSA Speak in improving students' speaking skills, b) Identify the benefits obtained by students from the application of ELSA Speak technology, c) Analyze the challenges and obstacles faced in the application of ELSA Speak for vocational English learning in the hospitality industry environment and d) The research results were presented objectively and in a structured manner, including data, analysis results, and output achievements.

3. Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the results of research on the application of ELSA Speak to improve the speaking skills of hospitality students. The findings presented answer the research problem formulation, obtained from data collected and analyzed according to the methodology in the previous chapter. The results will be presented objectively and in a structured manner.

Kupang State Polytechnic is one of the State Universities located in East Nusa Tenggara Province. This university has several departments and one of them is the Tourism Department. The Tourism Department consists of 2 (two) Study Programs, namely the Hospitality Study Program and the Travel and Tourism Business Study Program (UPW). In this study, the author focuses on the Hospitality Study Program, especially 5th semester Hotel students. Hospitality students are required to have good English language skills, especially in speaking skills because interaction with international guests is part of their work. Elsa Speak, as an AI-based application for pronunciation and conversation training, is considered potential to improve these skills. ELSA Speak (English Language Speech Assistant) is an artificial intelligence (AI)-based English learning application specifically designed to help users improve their speaking and pronunciation skills independently.

Based on the background and problem formulation, the author can describe several research findings as follows: 1) The use of Elsa Speak has proven quite effective in helping hospitality study program students improve their speaking skills in three main aspects: pronunciation, fluency, and intonation. The use of Elsa Speak also has a positive impact on improving the speaking skills of hospitality students. Improved scores on pronunciation, fluency, and confidence demonstrate that this AI-based application can be an effective learning tool for developing speaking skills. In terms of pronunciation, Elsa Speak is very helpful. This application uses speech recognition technology to detect specific pronunciation errors at the word, syllable, and even phoneme levels. ELSA Speak provides very detailed real-time feedback, allowing students to immediately know where their pronunciation errors lie and how to correct them. Clear pronunciation is crucial for hospitality students to be able to communicate effectively with international guests from various accent backgrounds, avoid misunderstandings, and convey information accurately.). This ability is very relevant to the demands of the hospitality world which emphasizes clarity, accuracy, and professionalism in oral communication. Based on the experience of several students as informants, they said that this application really helps them practice speaking without fear of mistakes or embarrassment. When they make mistakes in pronunciation, this application helps them how to pronounce it correctly. Students said that the speech feedback feature in this application works effectively in pointing out pronunciation errors and providing alternative correct pronunciations. Students said that usually they are shy or afraid of making mistakes when speaking English, but after using this application as a medium for independent learning, they became more courageous because they were immediately told which pronunciation was wrong and correct. This is in accordance with the theory of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) which states that learning technology provides a safe and interactive learning environment, thus encouraging learners to practice more actively without social pressure (Warschauer, 1996)

Based on students' experiences, this application helps them practice speaking without fear of mistakes or embarrassment. This aligns with the computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) theory, which states that learning technology provides a safe and interactive learning environment, encouraging learners to practice more actively without social pressure (Warschauer, 1996). It is also relevant to Morley's (1991) theory, which emphasizes that effective pronunciation instruction must provide immediate corrective feedback so learners can make improvements in a timely manner. ELSA provides this through acoustic assessments that can detect specific sound errors at the phoneme level. The second aspect related to speaking is fluency. ELSA Speak provides a safe and non-judgmental practice environment, which can reduce embarrassment or fear of mistakes when speaking. Students can practice repeatedly without social pressure, which is key to building fluency. Regarding the fluency aspect, some students stated that the dialogue-based exercises in this application provide an opportunity for them to practice quick responses, speaking rhythm, and appropriate word choice naturally. However, some students still feel that their fluency is not optimal. The author tried to ask about this, and they said that their main obstacle is related to their lack of vocabulary mastery. This has a significant and quite visible impact when they speak in front of the class. They appear hesitant in responding to conversations from their interlocutors. This is certainly a special note for researchers who are also English lecturers in the hospitality study program to focus more on improving students' vocabulary because increasing fluency or fluency directly impacts students' readiness to face the communication needs in the world of work, especially the hospitality world. The third aspect is intonation. In addition to pronunciation, ELSA Speak also analyzes intonation patterns and word stress in sentences. This application can provide feedback on how students' intonation sounds, whether it is appropriate to the context (for example, intonation of questions,

statements, or emotional expressions), thus helping them sound more natural and expressive like native speakers.

The results of the study also showed that the use of ELSA Speak helped students understand and master the intonation aspect. Students claimed to gain new insights into the use of word stress, the rising and falling patterns of pitch in sentences, and the difference in intonation between questions and statements. The intonation scoring feature in ELSA helped students assess whether their intonation was natural or still too flat. This is in accordance with Gilbert's opinion (2008) who stated that intonation is the core of communicative clarity, especially in service professions such as hospitality that require polite and friendly communication. In general, related to the intonation aspect, the author saw several shortcomings, especially for the interrogative form and also the accent or dialect of each student. Students who come from regions usually have an accent that is characteristic of them when speaking, both in Indonesian and English. The dialect or accent of their mother tongue greatly influences their speaking, especially their intonation when speaking English. In addition, for the interrogative form, there are still some students who make mistakes when speaking (Speaking) or reading texts (Reading). This is certainly also a special note for researchers because the right intonation is very important in conveying communication nuances, such as friendliness, empathy, or seriousness, all of which are vital aspects in customer service interactions in the hospitality industry. 2) The use of the Elsa Speak application provides significant benefits for students. This application is effectively used as a learning companion media in the classroom and as a tool for evaluating speaking skills objectively. This application also offers innovative solutions to overcome several obstacles to learning English and is also an effective tool for mastering speaking skills that are crucial for their careers. In addition to the general benefits, the following are specific benefits obtained by students: a) Students can improve their speaking skills comprehensively because they receive real-time feedback, b) More personalized and adaptive learning and adjust the learning path according to the needs of individual students. This means that each student can focus on their areas of weakness and learn at their own pace (individual learning), c) Increased self-confidence. With the existence of an environment for supportive practice and constructive feedback, students are expected to build confidence in speaking English (Speaking) and most importantly reduce embarrassment or fear of mistakes is one of the main keys to developing students' speaking skills (Speaking), d) Students can do independent practice anytime and anywhere without social pressure, e) The learning process is more efficient and effective with instant feedback and individual correction provided by the Elsa Speak application. Students can immediately find out and correct their mistakes, and speed up the learning process, f) Prepare themselves better and more mature for the world of work because students are taught and trained to speak in a more professional context. Students are expected to be ready to face the demands of cross-cultural and professional communication in the hospitality industry.

Referring to the background and problem formulation in the process of implementing the ELSA Speak application as a medium for learning speaking skills for students of the Hospitality study program, this study found several challenges and obstacles that affect the effectiveness of the application's use. Although ELSA Speak has generally been proven to help improve students' speaking skills, various technical, pedagogical, and personal obstacles still emerged during its implementation. This section describes these challenges in depth based on the results of interviews, observations, and other supporting data. The challenges and obstacles are both internal and external. Internally, they relate to the aspect of fluency. The researcher found that students are still not very fluent in speaking English. And based on the results of the observations, the author concluded that this is related to each student's vocabulary mastery. Speaking skills or speaking skills are language skills that require learners to be able to express ideas orally using appropriate language. One of the most important factors determining fluency is vocabulary

mastery. The relationship between the two is very strong and complementary. Both are like two sides of the same coin that are essential for effective oral communication. According to Thornbury (2005), fluency in speaking is achieved when learners can speak with minimal pauses, use contextually appropriate words, and construct appropriate sentences spontaneously. Thornbury (2005) emphasized that limited vocabulary is the most common factor hindering fluency in speaking. When learners lack the appropriate vocabulary, speaking speed slows down and long pauses occur, resulting in poor communication. The broader a student's vocabulary, the more fluent and spontaneous their speech becomes, especially in practical hospitality contexts such as greetings, offering help, and handling complaints. A strong vocabulary also helps in understanding what the other person is saying. Quick and accurate understanding allows for quicker and more relevant responses, keeping the conversation flowing smoothly and interactively. In addition to fluency, intonation is also a barrier to implementing this application. Broadly speaking, the author sees several shortcomings related to intonation, particularly in the interrogative form and the accent or dialect of each student. Students from regional areas usually have a distinctive accent when speaking, both in Indonesian and English. Their native dialect or accent significantly influences their English speaking, especially their intonation. Furthermore, some students still make errors in the interrogative form when speaking or reading. This is certainly a particular concern for researchers, as proper intonation is crucial in conveying nuances of communication, such as friendliness, empathy, or seriousness, all of which are vital aspects of customer service interactions in the hospitality industry. Speaking English is not just about grammar and vocabulary, but also intonation patterns. When speakers bring intonation patterns from their native language into English, a disruption called language interference or negative transfer often occurs.

Mother tongue influence (MTI) is a common phenomenon in second language acquisition. In the context of English learning, particularly in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) contexts like Indonesia, the mother tongue dialect often negatively impacts aspects of English prosody, including intonation, rhythm, and word stress. Intonation is the pattern of rising and falling vocal pitch that significantly determines meaning, expression, and clarity of communication in English. When the mother tongue dialect is too dominant, several intonation problems can arise and affect communication effectiveness. This is related to the problem encountered by researchers regarding interrogative sentences whose intonation is often incorrect. This is supported by the lack of pitch variation because Indonesian and mother tongues generally use flat intonation compared to English, which has a more dynamic intonation pattern. As a result, speakers influenced by these dialects often speak English with a flat intonation. The impact is that speech sounds less expressive or lacks appropriate emotion, and questions (yes-no questions) sound like statements due to the lack of pitch rising. Different languages have very specific intonation "tunes." If a speaker uses their native language tone, the result is a strong accent or altered pragmatic meaning (Intonational Phonology – Pierre humber (1980)). Errors in pragmatic meaning (intonation) not only change the literal meaning, but also the social meaning. Speakers can sound rude or angry unintentionally. This occurs when the intonation of the native language is used in an English context. This is related to the theory of pragmatics & speech act theory – Austin (1962), Searle (1969) which states that intonation influences the intent of the utterance (illocutionary force). L1 transfer of intonation can cause errors in conveying attitudes. Possible academic impacts include misunderstandings with foreign guests because when intonation is incorrect, the meaning can change, making communication ineffective. They may also find it difficult to follow Hospitality English standards because the hotel industry emphasizes warm greetings, clear instructions, and a courteous tone. Intonation errors can alter the quality of service.

Overall, the native language dialect has a significant negative impact on students' English intonation. From rhythm, stress, to pitch variation, these influences make speech less natural and sometimes lead to misunderstandings. In the hospitality context, intonation errors impact not only language comprehension but also professional image and the quality of communication with international guests. In addition to internal constraints, the author also identified external constraints related to the application's implementation, the most significant of which are limited internet access or expensive subscription fees. This application requires a stable internet connection to function optimally, especially for the speech recognition and real-time feedback features. Uneven internet access or high data rates in some areas can be significant barriers for students, especially if they are practicing off-campus. Furthermore, not all students have smartphones or other devices with adequate specifications and long-lasting batteries to run the Elsa Speak application smoothly. Expensive subscription fees are also a major contributing factor to the limitations of this application's use. Furthermore, this application has limitations in the free version. Some of Elsa Speak's best features are only available on Elsa Pro, so students using the free version experience limited access to advanced pronunciation exercises, interactive conversation or dialogue features, and English Hospitality-specific materials. This creates an uneven learning experience between students using the paid version and those using the free version. Furthermore, the relevance of the content to the specific needs of the hospitality industry is also questionable. While the app is excellent for general English, it may be limited in content specific to hospitality communication scenarios (e.g., check-in/check-out, assisting guests with complaints, explaining hotel amenities). If the available content is less relevant to their vocational needs, students may find the app less useful for immediate career preparation. These external constraints need to be considered and addressed for ELSA Speak to be effective and provide maximum benefit to hospitality students.

4. Conclusion

This study evaluated the effectiveness of the artificial intelligence (AI) application ELSA Speak in improving the English-speaking skills of students in the Hospitality Study Program at Kupang State Polytechnic. The primary objective was to improve pronunciation, fluency, and intonation, while supporting cross-cultural communication competencies, which are crucial in the hospitality industry.

The results showed that ELSA Speak proved effective as an interactive learning medium. The application helped students improve pronunciation, increased speaking confidence, and enabled independent practice with detailed, real-time feedback. This contributed to innovative AI-based English language learning that is relevant to industry needs.

However, this study also identified several significant obstacles, including: a) Pedagogical Aspects: Lack of vocabulary mastery, intonation issues influenced by regional dialects and mother tongue interference, and suboptimal fluency levels, b) Technical and Infrastructure Aspects: Unstable or uneven internet access, low device specifications, and limited features in the free version and expensive subscription fees and c) Personal Aspects: Lack of student discipline in optimally utilizing the application.

Overall, ELSA Speak offers great potential as an innovative English language learning tool. However, to achieve optimal effectiveness and greater relevance to the needs of the hospitality industry, a comprehensive strategy is needed to address identified technical, pedagogical, and personal barriers, as well as a follow-up plan to maximize the use of AI technology in vocational education.

Acknowledgements

Thanks to God Almighty for all His blessings, grace, and guidance, enabling the successful completion of this research, entitled Implementation of ELSA Speak in English Language Learning to Improve the Speaking Skills of Hospitality Students in the Tourism Department of Kupang State Polytechnic.

The researcher expresses his deepest appreciation and gratitude to:

1. The Director of Kupang State Polytechnic, who provided the opportunity and support for this research.
2. The Head of P3M, who provided the author with the opportunity to participate in this routine research.
3. The Head of the Tourism Department and all staff who facilitated the research process, both administratively and academically
4. The Head of the Hospitality Study Program, who provided permission, direction, and support throughout the research.
5. All lecturers and staff of the Tourism Department, who directly and indirectly contributed to the smooth running of this research.
6. The Hospitality Study Program students who participated as research subjects with enthusiasm, discipline, and excellent cooperation throughout the learning and data collection process.
7. Other parties who cannot be mentioned individually have provided assistance, support, and contributions to the completion of this research.

The researcher realizes that this research still has limitations and is far from perfect. Therefore, constructive criticism and suggestions are highly appreciated for future improvements. Finally, the researcher hopes that the results of this research will be beneficial for the development of English language learning, particularly in the hospitality sector, and serve as a reference for further research.

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